

FOSSR

FOSTERING OPEN SCIENCE IN SOCIAL SCIENCE RESEARCH

DELIVERABLE 8.1

PLANNING DOCUMENT FOR THE ACTIVITIES RELATED TO THE CAPACITY BUILDING AND TRAINING

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<i>Abstract</i>	This deliverable introduces the portfolio of training activities foreseen in the context of WP8 of the FOSSR project and demonstrates the achievement of milestones 1-2-3 related to their general planning. The types of training activities, their objectives and formats, and associated management activities will be discussed. The general planning is complemented by the WP8 list of milestones and deliverables.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The background mission of the FOSSR project relies on creating and strengthening awareness and knowledge of data and methodologies used in empirical social sciences among a wide audience, through maintaining and reinforcing of relevant Research Infrastructures (RI), while fostering the development of a research and social environment conducive to an open, shared and simplified data access via innovative interfaces. The project will concretely contribute to the effective implementation of the ‘open science’ for social science researchers by providing innovative tools and services for research, shared virtual environment for data access and a wide and varied package of training courses, sessions and programmes (FOSSR DoW, 2022).

FOSSR adopts the common theme of the development of Open Science in the Italian context with the goal of creating a framework of tools and services for the social science scholar community involving the RIs in social sciences coordinated by CNR, namely CESSDA, SHARE and RISIS. The framework should take the form of an integrated knowledge sharing platform, a single point of access to all the tools and services made available by the Italian nodes of social science infrastructures.

FOSSR fosters the building of an Italian Open Science Cloud, along the lines of the European Open Science Cloud project, in which to integrate innovative services developed by the project for data collection, data curation and fairness and data analysis on economic and societal change.

FOSSR wants to promote toward multiple audiences, a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favorable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces.

1.1 FOSSR objectives and ambition

FOSSR has the general aim of promoting, towards multiple audiences, a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, by providing (i) systematic and organized knowledge (also through summary harmonized data) about available social science data resources in Italian data archives, especially the CESSDA Archive, already object of the grand infrastructural proposal; (ii) resources supporting methodological advancement as to data collection and data analysis, especially important for RISIS to understand the design, the implementation, and the outcome of research and innovation policies, which can improve the robustness of empirical evidence produced for policy makers and to deal with new research questions, and (iii) tools and services to make publicly available advanced probability panels for longitudinal analyses to support important survey such as SHARE, complementing them with a network of online laboratories. The integration of this pool of resources shall concretely contribute to the realization of open science for scholars in social sciences, going with an important program of scientific training for the production and analysis of social science based on FAIR empirical data.

One further key objective is setting a new generation of young researchers in social sciences, by hiring several researchers and technologists with fixed time contracts, which will become

highly skilled human resources in data science and data management in social science research, and by funding 20 PhD positions to train early career researchers in the field.

FOSSR is also aimed at fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favorable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces (data exploration portals, time series, interactive visualizations), and through online data analysis software aimed at students, along with divulgation resources about social science methodology. These aspects are particularly aimed at civil society organizations (NGOs, etc.), students, ordinary citizens, to foster a widespread societal awareness of social science data, results, methods to promote an easier and more user-friendly dissemination.

The main investment shall be on the creation of a suitable IT infrastructure and a network of data center to provide researchers access online and onsite, and to support the workflow of the proposed collaborative projects. One of the subsequent goals of FOSSR will be to develop innovative tools and services for data collection and data analyses, and to support participating users in the acquisition and use of advanced equipment and software for social science research needed for collaborative studies and projects. The achievement of the above-mentioned goals can be reached by means of an online platform – the Open Cloud, acting also as a dissemination layer, intermediating between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring access intermediating between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring access also to multiple software interfaces, geared at different audiences, methodological content, and training materials.

1.2 Purpose and scope of this document

The present deliverable introduces the framework of the training activities envisioned in the context of the **Work Package 8 (WP8) “Capacity building and training”** of the FOSSR project and demonstrates the achievement of the 1-2-3 milestones associated with the WP (see Section 7).

Delivering a set of training activities is critical in the context of promoting the contents and services of a RIs. The development of innovative data collection and analysis methods, as envisaged in the FOSSR project’s WPs 3-4-5, as well as new ways to access data and use related services, as proposed by WP6, will have a significant impact on the social science community if accompanied by actions and initiatives to broaden the pool of research actors and stakeholders who will acquire and empower knowledge of them and, as a result, establish new applications for the novel resources.

The WP8 is intended to offer **a set of diverse training initiatives**, at various level, to enhance individual skills in maximizing the potential of infrastructures involved in FOSSR by utilizing various advanced tools for data collection, analysis and managing, and strategies to address novel research questions. The training supply will be directed at the RIs' diverse audiences, including scholars, early-career researchers, students, practitioners, policymakers, officers, and government workers.

The initiatives will be articulated in three macro-categories:

1. **Online Training Courses** (foreseen by **WP8 - Task 1**) on specific topics related to data collection, managing and processing that can have also the effect of encouraging researchers and interested audience to access the infrastructure data;

2. **Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions** (foreseen by **WP8 - Task 2**) aimed at learning how the efforts of researchers can tackle the societal actors' need and infrastructure data can produce social effects;
3. **Course at Master level and positions at PhD level** (foreseen by **WP8 - Task 3**), for the acquisition of titles pertaining to the third cycle of the Bologna process (Level 8 EQF), i.e. a course at Master level on applied data science and twenty PhD positions to be opened at various Italian universities.

Section 2 of this document describes the variety of training opportunities envisioned by WP Tasks 1-2-3; Section 3 discusses the objectives and format of training activities expected by Tasks 1 and 2; and Section 4 describes their management activities. Section 5 goes into detail about the opportunities envisioned by Task 3. Section 6 describes WP Task 4 focused on developing an online data analysis training software, a resource that can support targeted data analysis and specific educational needs. Section 7 summarizes the Milestones, Key Performance Indicators, and Timing of the WP8 of the FOSSR project. Finally, Section 8 presents the document's conclusions, and Section 9 lists the acronyms used throughout the text.

2. THE SUPPLY OF TRAINING INITIATIVES WITHIN FOSSR

RIs should boost research by generating a range of positive impacts on the ability of researchers to conduct excellent studies, on meeting the needs of social and political stakeholders, and ultimately bring benefits to society as a whole. Consequently, the training of scientists and professionals should be prioritized because it can effectively provide people with the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to use and benefit from scientific data.

Training in new methods, techniques, and technologies for data collection, management, preservation, and analysis is an essential factor in conducting cutting-edge research, promoting social innovation, and strengthening synergies between scholarly activities and social actors. Furthermore, while training those who can directly benefit from infrastructure in research work is important, new models of collaboration and reflexivity between scholars and people working outside the research sector are needed to stimulate effects for better defining research in terms of research questions and topics to explore in the interest of society.

2.1 Diversification of training opportunities

FOSSR is committed to supporting the education of the next generation of data scientists, enhancing the skills of scholars and stakeholders in accessing, analyzing, managing, querying and interpreting data, and fostering reflective learning and interactions between researchers and societal actors.

WP8, coordinated by CNR-IRCrES, will offer a variety of training opportunities throughout the project's duration. The portfolio is detailed as follows:

1. **Online Training Courses (OTC)**, managed by CNR-IRPPS (UO4), include:
 - **Methodological Courses (MC)** aimed at improving knowledge related to the application of advanced statistical methods and techniques,
 - **Research Data Management Courses (RDMC)**, addressed to social science researchers who want to acquire skills to manage and share data in compliance with FAIR principles;

2. **Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions - henceforth Participatory Sessions (PS)** -, managed by CNR-IRCrES (UO2), include:
 - **Learning Sessions (LS)** to share perspectives on how to use FOSSR-related infrastructures in the research practice and knowledge generated by data can be translated to produce social impact;
 - **Action Research Sessions (ARS)** to create new knowledge on the value of societal actors to influence scientific actors in social science research, empowering the link between the research and society;
3. **Course at Master level and positions at PhD level**, jointly coordinated by CNR-ISMED and CNR-IRCrES (UO14 and UO2), which foresee, according to the approved DoW, the creation of:
 - **1 course at Master level on data science applied to social science research** that will provide advanced training for two years at an Italian university;
 - **20 PhD Positions** to be opened at Italian universities within the thirty-ninth Italian doctoral cycle, to train a highly skilled new generation of data scientists.

3. DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVES AND FORMAT OF ONLINE TRAINING COURSES (METHODOLOGICAL COURSES AND RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT COURSES) AND PARTICIPATORY SESSIONS (LEARNING SESSIONS AND ACTION RESEARCH SESSIONS)

The format of Online Short Courses (OTC) and Participatory Sessions (PS, including Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions) address some of the major goals related to the FOSSR project's mission: (i) developing and strengthening individual skills in utilizing the potential of infrastructures, using various types of advanced tools and techniques to address innovative research questions; (ii) providing expertise in managing the research data lifecycle; (iii) promoting and encouraging productive interactions between knowledge producers and with stakeholders with an eye toward the social effect of research.

OTCs, managed by CNR-IRPPS (UO4), are of two types - Methodological Courses (MC) and Research Data Management Courses (RDMC), and will be proposed and organized by the CNR institutes involved in the FOSSR project (henceforth "FOSSR partners") in response of a permanent call of proposal; PSs are divided into Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions, and will be conducted by CNR-IRCrES (UO2) and organized based on expressions of educational needs from FOSSR partners.

For the entire duration of the FOSSR project, **10 training initiatives including OTCs and PSs**, all free of charge for participants, are foreseen (see Section 7). A total of **6 online training courses** (MC+RDMC) is expected, with a participation of 150 attendees. A total of **4 participatory sessions** (LS+ARS) is expected, with a participation of 80 attendees.

The sub-paragraphs that follow describe the specific features of each format.

3.1 Methodological Courses (MC)

Methodological Courses provide basic and advanced knowledge about the content of the FOSSR infrastructure, data collection and processing. The primary aim is to **transfer**

knowledge on quantitative methods and techniques to scholars, researchers and stakeholders on how to use data more creatively and play a role in educating those in the social sciences community who are hesitant to use quantitative approaches.

Online methodological courses are two or three-day on-line courses designed to deepen specific advanced methodologies for data collection, advanced statistical methods and techniques and data analysis, with a special attention to the ones developed within the FOSSR project:

- innovative solutions for data collection developed in WP3 (i.e. allowing the execution of surveys in compliance with the highest standards of privacy and security of personal data and quality);
- the new tools to develop high quality longitudinal and panel data on the Italian population developed in WP4;
- the new methods, developed in WP5, for data analysis, knowledge integration and representation based on the most recent solutions in statistical modelling, complex modelling, deep learning, and knowledge engineering.

MCs will be addressed to the following categories:

- scholars, early-career researchers, students in the social science field;
- scholars, early-career researchers, students from other neighboring R&D fields;
- researchers and officers of relevant organizations, in particular those representing R&I Performers and Research Funding Organizations;
- representatives from public institutions, National Statistical Offices, European Statistical Units, organizations dealing with research and innovation and stakeholders from civil society organizations.

Courses' structure is expected to provide a well balanced mix of frontal/theoretical lessons and more interactive activities supported by tutoring: spaces of 'creative training' as laboratories, where the trainers shall stimulate the trainees to reflect on their data needs and research questions, through direct participative technique.

Each course should provide working sessions on one of the FOSSR resources.

They will be provided in synchronous mode through a virtual meeting and working space platform. To guarantee a wider impact, the educational resources and documents associated to each online course will remain freely available on the FOSSR website.

MCs are expected to enhance social scientists' use of quantitative approaches in particular related to the use of research infrastructures for surveys, advanced methodologies for data collection and data analysis (e.g. use of longitudinal data, spatial models, text mining) based on the most recent solutions in statistical modelling, complex modelling, deep learning, with special attention to quantitative techniques to be applied to data from the infrastructures involved in the project.

The courses should also have the effect of encouraging researchers and interested audience to access the infrastructure data.

3.2 Research Data Management Courses (RDMC)

Another type of Online Training Course will be provided in reference to the **issues related to Data Management** and data lifecycle in the research-related processes. Online courses on

Research Data Management are two or three-day online courses aimed at enhancing researchers' and social scientists awareness and skills in using large datasets, producing and collecting empirical data compliant with:

- FAIR principles, GDPR rules, ethical aspects;
- standards that facilitate the semantic and technical interoperability among systems and organizations.

so as to prepare a generation of researchers able to use and produce quality datasets and continuously enrich the Italian Open Science Cloud for the Social Sciences.

Providing links with FOSSR datasets and infrastructure, they will cover the following topics: data management plan, GDPR management, data organization, data documentation, legal and ethical aspects, data preservation, data access and publication, reuse of research data, data communication.

RDMCs will be addressed to participants among the following categories:

- scholars, early-career researchers, students in the social science field and other neighboring R&D fields;
- researchers and officers of relevant organizations, in particular those representing R&I Performers.

In terms of structure, as for the Methodological Courses, Research Data Management Courses are expected to provide a well balanced mix of frontal/theoretical lessons and more interactive activities supported by tutoring. They will be provided in synchronous mode through a virtual meeting and working space platform. To guarantee a wider impact, the educational resources and documents associated to each online course will remain freely available on the FOSSR website.

As for the expected outcomes, Research Data Management Courses are expected to increase social scientists' use of skills and competences related to make data sharable and compliant with FAIR principles, GDPR rules, data organization, data documentation, legal and ethical constraints, data preservation.

3.3 Learning Sessions (LS)

Most scholars have learned about research processes, as well as the development of research skills and possibilities for application, through *formal training* in the form of courses or programmes, in which a tutor or team of teachers have provided information on the subject of study. However, part of the knowledge and skills is also acquired directly through *daily research work*, coming up against actual problems, limitations and the need for solutions. In some circumstances, these types of knowledge acquisition, which we could make coincide with the concepts of *education* and *experience*, could prove to be insufficient in the presence of completely new needs or the availability of new opportunities and when the environmental and relational resources are not suitable for finding effective ways to approach them.

The objective of the Learning Sessions is to allow the emergence of **training needs** related to concrete social research possibilities or practices related to the information wealth and **research potential of the FOSSR-related infrastructures**, give them a voice and stimulate the learning and the search for solutions through a collaborative interaction with peers and experts. Participatory learning differs from teacher-centered methodologies in which students sit passively at desks, answer closed questions, and copy from presentations. In these sessions

participants are actively involved: they propose the object of learning, create the questions or projects, carry them out, and then evaluate and grade their peers' solutions.

This kind of approach follows the constructivist theories of learning, for which knowledge is actively *constructed* rather than transmitted and people learn by actively building their understanding by applying their knowledge to *meaningful problems*. Engaging participants during the sessions can include the stimulation of discussions, proposing problem-solving case studies, creating role plays and other methods. All is targeted to stimulate critical thinking. Participants will learn together concepts through interactivity, reflection (asking and answer questions) or by working together to solve concrete problems.

Participatory learning sessions wants to promote active learning with the guide of an instructor and the participation of experts on how to use FOSSR-related infrastructures, services or methods in the research practice, particularly for tackling for societal issues. For example, they will allow participants to meet in participative events for learning together and finding solution on topics related to:

- how peculiar designs of social research with the application of specific quantitative methods or techniques could address relevant societal issues;
- how to implement mixed methods to address complex topics that need the integration of different approaches;
- how to apply specific tools developed by FOSSR to socially-relevant research questions.

Through the dialogue between participants, the guide of an instructor and the presence of experts in the audience the specific value of the infrastructures and methods and services related will be discussed in terms of potential applications to produce social impact.

The initiatives will be managed by CNR-IRCrES (UO2) and organized based on a collection of *expressions of interest* about specific educational needs related to the research infrastructures. They will last 2 or 3 days, depending on the quantity of training needs collected on a general topic and will be organized preferably in presence mode. Hybrid form and online formats could be also taken in consideration.

The format presented in this document is a preliminary plan that is subject to changes and revisions.

Target of the LSs are:

- researchers and scholars in the field of social research;
- researchers and scholars from other disciplines interested in interdisciplinary collaboration;
- non-academic users and stakeholders with an interest on the topics proposed or wanting to share their experience on the exploitation of research for society.

Expected outcome is to attract scholars on FOSSR data, methods and services to address relevant societal issues.

3.4 Action Research Sessions (ARS)

The Action Research Sessions, like the Learning Sessions, depart from traditional training models where the teacher sits in the front and imparts knowledge to the students, who are

merely passive recipients. Action Research Sessions are conceived as a highly contextualized learning strategy for **empowering the link between the research and society** with a **transformative effect** for researchers and stakeholders. This format joins together the *users of the knowledge* and the *researchers* in the same learning process, as a process in which new knowledge is built on the diversity of experiences and perspectives of the involved actors.

Sessions will be particularly focused on how to introduce changes related to

- how the efforts of researchers could be better defined in terms of research questions and topics by using research infrastructures and tools and methods developed within FOSSR;
- how the results of research related to the research infrastructures involved in FOSSR can be exploited for the benefit of society;
- how to develop the contents of the research infrastructures with implications for desirable societal impacts.

The sessions will trigger mechanisms of reflexivity and will produce ideas for the future of the infrastructures, services and application related to the FOSSR project. They should lead to processes of self-transformation within groups that are stimulated by debate and interaction between academics and stakeholders, strengthening the connection between empirical social science and society.

The initiatives will be developed by CNR-IRCrES (UO2) personnel, based on expressions of specific interest by FOSSR partners. Sessions might foresee 2 or 3 meeting over 1 week, but the final structure will be planned with the action research session conductor in charge, based on the best strategy related to the learning process.

The format presented in this document is a preliminary plan that is subject to changes and revisions.

Participants of ARS will be:

- researchers and scholars in the field of social research;
- researchers and scholars from other disciplines interested in interdisciplinary collaboration;
- different types of stakeholders (e.g., representatives from the political sector, private non-profit research associations, companies, intermediary agencies and other interested organizations).

4. MANAGEMENT OF ONLINE TRAINING COURSES AND PARTICIPATORY SESSIONS

Management activities related to Online Training Courses (OTC) are in charge of CNR-IRPPS (UO4). In general, it is expected that all FOSSR partners can submit proposals for organizing OSCs, and that the proposal will include contents or topics from WP3-WP4-WP5-WP6 and relate to the infrastructures involved in FOSSR. Partners involved in FOSSR can organize the trainings in partnership mode; all partners can participate in specific lectures or modules within trainings.

Management activities related to Participatory Sessions (PS) are in charge of CNR-IRCrES (UO2). The session will be conducted by CNR-IRCrES personnel and based on expressions of

educational needs from RISIS partners related to FOSSR infrastructures and project services and achievements.

4.1 Operational activities

The operational activities, related to OTCs and PSs, will include:

- Preparing the following formats/templates:
 - proposal scheme for MCs and RDMCs available for the partners,
 - ‘expression of educational needs’ scheme for LSs and ARSs,
 - application forms for potential attendees,
 - reporting templates to be filled from the organizers of the trainings;
- Collecting the short Final Report on each training;
- Elaborate the format of a questionnaire for assessing the trainings;
- Managing a repository of participants and materials;
- Preparing a summary for the annual FOSSR DAYS.

The selection process of the attendees of the courses is delegated to the organizers of the courses; likewise, the administration and elaboration of the questionnaire course is delegated to the organizers of the courses. The organizers are also in charge of the dissemination of the initiative promoted in coordination with the strategy of WP9.

4.2 Proposals and requirements

OTCs. A process for submission and assessment of the requirements for the training proposals coming from the FOSSR partners will be implemented. A call for proposals will be circulated between the FOSSR partners. Proposals will be submitted using dedicated formats for MCs and RDMCs, including dates, details about the content of the training and infrastructure(s) involved, an articulated programme, targeted audience (specific skills requested to the participants), facilities supplied to the attendees;

PSs. Expressions of educational needs from FOSSR partners will be required through a scheme with must highlight the aim of the training and the relevance of the issue proposed for FOSSR.

Proposals and expressions of educational needs can be submitted anytime along the duration of the project and will be submitted to: **training.fossr@ircres.cnr.it**.

The approval of the proposals for MCs and RDMCs and the consideration for expressions of interest for LSs and ARSs are in charge of a **Training Committee** composed by:

- Dr. Andrea Orazio Spinello (WP8 Leader);
- Dr. Adriana Valente (WP8-Task1 Leader);
- Dr. Emanuela Reale (Scientific Coordinator of the FOSSR Project).

Proposals for OTCs will be assessed on the basis of the following requirements:

- Background of the subject(s) in charge of the training activities;
- Clarity of the proposal, clear added value of the course and relevance for the FOSSR aims;

- Precise identification of the targeted audience, considering that in case of courses based on advanced statistics, the audience shall have enough competences in order to benefit of the course;
- Facilities provided to the participants;
- In accordance with the NPRR principles: gender balance strategy and strategies adopted to enhance the participation of students from southern regions;
- Accessibility strategy: the training must be accessible for a wide community (including those outside the users' community);
- Inclusion strategy: how the participation of potential participants with fewer opportunities is enhanced and promoted;
- Methodological approach: level of students' participation and interactivity of the training;
- The applicant should explain how to assess the final level of knowledge acquired by participants during the course. It is welcome to include in the course practical and interactive exercises that also have the aim of (formative) evaluation. Otherwise, the applicant must explain the tools for assessment chosen (e.g.: final tests or composition);
- Presence of updated documentation to be supplied to the students (the documentation for Applied Courses is supposed to be updated according to the changes of the datasets and platforms);
- Sustainability: how the course may be reused by the scientific, educational and civil communities?;
- Communication strategy: the applicant is in charge to promote his/her own course, synergies with WP9 can be activated.

The idea is not to have a traditional “selection process”, rather a constructive process involving Committee in charge of training management and the proposers, so that their proposals fit better with the FOSSR approaches.

Expressions of educational needs for LSs and ARSs will be considered on the basis of the following requirements:

- Clarity of the proposal;
- Relevance for the FOSSR aims;
- An elevate possibility of interactions among the participants;
- Focus on specific learning contents to be exploited using services related to the FOSSR infrastructures.

The organizers of all approved training activities will be required to have participants complete an evaluation questionnaire and produce a short course report.

4.3 Communication on the website and via social media

A space on the FOSSR website, managed within the WP9, will be dedicated to the OTCs and PSs, with all the information available.

More specifically, the website will provide:

- list of training opportunities open with information on aims, contents, deadline for application, etc. (downloadable documents for people that want to apply);
- list of courses done with information on aims, contents, link to the materials uploaded on Zenodo, reporting and assessment;

All the information regarding the training opportunities will be also circulated via social media channels activated within WP9.

5. COURSE AT MASTER LEVEL AND POSITIONS AT PHD LEVEL

5.1 Course at Master level

Supporting the education of the next generation of data scientists, FOSSR WP8 will fund a **course at Master level (*Master Universitario*) on data science applied to the social sciences** intended as a programme that promote a widespread knowledge of methodologies used in the empirical social sciences and the training of a new generation of young researchers with strong expertise in the application to social science of techniques of data collection, processing, analysis, visualization, reporting in a variety of situation. The Master programme will be created at a prestigious Italian university and will allow to acquire a title pertaining to the third cycle of the Bologna process (Level 8 EQF).

For the activation of this particularly innovative Master, it was necessary to identify a suitable university. The **University of Milan Bicocca** was found to be a particularly suitable one. In fact, together with the CNR, **the university is the national node of the European research infrastructure CESSDA, one of the three research infrastructures composing the network to be reinforced through the FOSSR project**. Among the missions of CESSDA there is the facilitation in teaching and learning in the social sciences. Putting together the objectives of CESSDA and the FOSSR project, the University, with its many years of experience in the field of specific research and training activities, appeared therefore the ideal candidate for the establishment of the Master.

Following an invitation from the leader unit of WP8 (CNR-IRCrES protocol no. 0000786_2022 of 22 November 2022), an expression of interest to organize the Master Programme was received from **University of Milan Bicocca, Department of Sociology and Social Research** (CNR-IRCrES protocol no. 0000789_2022 of 23 November 2022). The aforementioned department presented a detailed proposal for structuring a **Second-level Master Programme (*Master di Secondo Livello*)**, suggesting a new name – **Master in “Social Data Science”** – instead of “Master of Applied Data Science”, as foreseen in the Project DoW. Thus, the organization of the Master programme will be entrusted to the University of Milan Bicocca following the signing of an agreement within the already existing Framework Agreement between the University of Milan Bicocca and the National Research Council of 14 May 2019. The signing of the agreement is the subject of Milestone 4 (see Section 7).

The Master in “Social Data Science” (SDS) is foreseen as a two-year master course taught in English that combines social sciences and computer science, in which the analysis of Big Data and the use of Artificial Intelligence algorithms are linked to social scientific theory and analysis. SDS will provide a solid foundation in Data Science for students with a social science degree. The main emphasis in the course is on computational science within a robust framework of social science applications and research design principles. Furthermore, the Master will give an overview of the current opportunities and reach of computational social science.

Students with a social science background will be trained to use data to answer social science questions. Students are assumed to have taken an introductory course in quantitative methods or applied statistics at a basic level, although this is not a formal requirement. Students will take different project-based programming courses designed for those without a standard computing or statistical background.

For student new to computational methods, it will be a chance to develop the competencies needed today, increasingly in-demand in the job market. These skills will provide innovativeness and originality to student work for years to come. This is also an opportunity for students new to the social sciences to see where computational and statistical skills can go with innovative applications to issues of great societal concern.

The main goal of the Master programme is to illustrate what computational social sciences are about and their main applications. In particular, it will illustrate how information can be gained by studying the huge digital imprint left by today's social interactions, what the world of machine learning is all about, including the basic concepts behind this current driver of much of the computational landscape. Finally, attention will be placed on the power of social networks and, on explaining how computer simulation helps us untangle some of the major contemporary social challenges.

Areas of interest of the Master programme. Epistemology; Social Science Theories; Fundamentals of Social Science Research Design; Fundamentals of Computer Programming & Algorithms; Digital Sociology; Digital Data for Data Scientists; Ontologies and the Semantic Web; Big Data; Artificial Intelligence; Machine learning; Open Data; R and Python Programming; Natural Language Processing; Data-driven applications; Internet of things; Managing and Visualizing Data; Computational linguistics; Equity; Data Colonization; Responsibility.

Course structure. The Master programme is expected to start on autumn 2023 and structured over two years in which the first year provides training in the main aspects of applied data science, computation and programming, and quantitative methods by providing the foundation for the topics covered in the second year. The Master programme involves the acquisition of 120 CFUs for the two years and consists of around 750 hour of classes (also, or exclusively, in remote mode: to be defined) and laboratory and stage activities. In the first year, training is provided in the main aspects of applied data science, computation and programming, and quantitative methods, building a foundation for their application on the analysis of topics covered in the second year. This cross-disciplinary introduction to sociology, social research methodologies, computer science, statistics and linguistics will build a strong foundation for their application and analyses in the second year. The Master teachers will be selected based on their specific expertise in the planned areas of teaching and attention will be paid to gender balance. Further aspects on the course structure are being examined by the proponents.

Criteria for admission to the Master programme. Admission to the Master programme is free of charge and reserved to a total of 20/25 students holding a master's degree who will be selected on the basis of an interview where in addition to motivation, knowledge of some basic topics of social research methodology and statistics will be assessed. Attention will be paid to the region of origin of students, particularly for those from Southern Italy in accordance to NRRP goals, and gender balance.

5.2 PhD Positions

According to the project DoW approved, the FOSSR project will fund **twenty PhD positions** in doctoral courses at various Italian universities during the thirty-ninth Italian doctoral cycle (*39° ciclo di dottorato*). The positions will be assigned in response to research project proposal coherent to the themes of the FOSSR project, with the goal of developing advanced skills in the field of social sciences, fostering effective research methodologies, allowing advanced analysis of complex data sets, and preparing to a complex use of statistical software.

PhD positions are valuable in feeding a new generation of scholars who can use the resources provided by the RIs involved in FOSSR by combining strong theoretical, methodological, and technical knowledge, as well as being aware of the legal issues related to data processing.

For PhD positions, candidates will be required to submit research projects related to social sciences or methodological issues on topics developed by the FOSSR project, such as Innovation in data collection (WP3), Longitudinal studies (WP4), Innovation in data analysis: knowledge extraction, integration, and enrichment (WP5), Data access services related to research infrastructure (WP6).

The PhD positions will be realized through specific agreements with universities with which the CNR has already signed the General Agreement for Research Cooperation. The stipulation of the agreements will be preceded by the sending of a letter of intent sent to universities by the CNR institutes involved in FOSSR interested in activating the positions. The final list of universities and related doctoral courses where to activate the positions is currently being defined.

Agreements with universities will be completed at M8 (June 2023, Milestone 5, see Section 7).

The PhD positions will be activated within the Italian *39° ciclo di dottorato* (from academic year 2023/2024).

In accordance with Ministerial Decree no. 1141 of 7 October 2021 by MUR, within projects financed under the funding scheme “*Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca*” the Consortium must ensure compliance with constraints arising from the NRRP about gender inequality, thus at least 40% of PhD grants must be awarded to female researchers.

N.B. We are currently awaiting some clarifications from the MUR, which could result in a new planning of the PhD positions, including a reduction in their number.

6. ONLINE DATA ANALYSIS SOFTWARE FOR TRAINING

In the context of WP8, the overall objective of Task 8.4, starting from M9 and managed by CNR-ISTC (UO6), is to design, develop and make available a web-based interactive and collaborative computational environment for supporting users in defining, documenting and running data analytics tasks. The tool will be conceived as a cloud-based platform that will provide a full-fledged **online training and learning environment**, as a basis for supporting the delivery of **introductory data analysis courses for the social sciences** in the context of tailored training programmes. The platform thus targets training instructors, students and junior researchers, with the aim of lowering the barriers that prevent non-technical users from approaching data analytics tasks.

To enable the definition and management of virtual laboratories and e-learning resources for teaching the foundations of data analytics, the platform will compose and integrate different

capabilities and services and, where possible, off-the-shelf components and tools will be reused or customized. To support access control and user management, the tool will integrate open platform access control solutions and existing security frameworks. This will enable the definition of basic authentication and authorization policies for access control to the platform and its resources, as well as to define and manage virtual labs with restricted access. The platform will support and make available various data analysis tools and languages, with a focus on programming languages and frameworks that offer wide support for data analytics, such as Python, R, Stata, etc. Users will be able to collaboratively write, document and interactively run data analysis scripts in an execution environment that combines live code editing, explanatory text and documentation, dashboards and data visualizations. The platform will allow using and experimenting with a set of pre-defined data analysis and visualization techniques, without requiring advanced programming skills. To deal with large and complex datasets as a basis for data analytics, the platform will allow transparently accessing distributed file systems and big data sources, leveraging analytics engines for large-scale data processing such as Apache Hadoop and Spark. By combining access control policies and data analytics capabilities, the environment will also allow dealing with the management and analysis of sensitive datasets. This will enable social scientists to learn the importance of data security and privacy, and deal with the potential sensitivity of the datasets to be analyzed with controlled data access and sharing procedures.

From a general perspective, the implementation and provision of this platform will directly exploit and benefit from the physical infrastructure and the overall cloud layer built on top of it, as addressed in WP7 and WP6. With respect to the activities of WP8, the platform will support the targeted data analysis and educational needs that characterize the planned training activities. In particular, the platform could be used and made available in the context of the methodological and research data management courses (Task 8.1, see par. 3.1), as well as in the context of the Second-level Master programme (Task 8.3, see par. 5.1). Specifically, the platform and its virtual labs could be actively used in the courses and be customized to support the Master programme with the inclusion and provision of tailored contents and services. This includes the set up and configuration of data analysis tools, datasets, customized data views and other digital instruments contextualized and tuned with respect to the needs and goals of the training courses.

7. MILESTONES, KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS AND TIMING

The WP8 - “Capacity building and training”, coordinated by CNR-IRCRES (UO2), is structured into 4 tasks:

- Task 8.1: *Online training courses* - Leader: CNR IRPPS (UO4);
- Task 8.2: *Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions* - Leader: CNR IRCRES (UO2);
- Task 8.3: *Course at Master level and positions at PhD level* - Leaders: CNR ISMED (UO14) and CNR-IRCrES (UO2);
- Task 8.4: *Online data analysis software for training* – Leader: CNR ISTC (UO6).

Below is the list of milestones to be pursued (see FOSSR DoW), with an indication of the task to which they refer, the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) expected and the reference deadline.

Table 1 – Milestones and KPIs related to WP8.

<i>Milestone number</i>	<i>Milestone</i>	<i>WP Task</i>	<i>KPI</i>	<i>Deadline</i>
1	Setting of the format for the online courses (MCs and RDMs)	Task 8.1	Format for the online courses (MCs and RDMs)	Bimester 1 December 2022
2	Setting of the format for the Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions	Task 8.2	Format for the Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions	Bimester 1 December 2022
3	Planning of the course at Master level and PhD courses at universities	Task 8.3	Planning of the course at Master level and PhD courses at universities	Bimester 1 December 2022
4	Agreement with university for the course at Master level	Task 8.3	Signing of the agreement with university for the course at Master level	Bimester 4 June 2023
5	Agreements with universities for PhD positions	Task 8.3	Signing of the agreements with universities for PhD positions	Bimester 4 June 2023
6	Definition of requirements for online data analysis software for training	Task 8.4	Identification of requirements for online data analysis	Bimester 6 October 2023
7	Definition of unit and integration tests online data analysis software for training	Task 8.4	Definition of unit and integration tests	Bimester 8 February 2024
8	First 3 Online courses delivered (MCs and RDMs)	Task 8.1	3 courses delivered 75 attendees involved	Bimester 9 April 2024
9	First release of the online data analysis software for training	Task 8.4	Release of the online data analysis software for training	Bimester 9 April 2024
10	First 2 Learning session/Action Research Sessions delivered	Task 8.2	2 Learning session/ Action Research Sessions delivered; 40 participants involved	Bimester 9 April 2024
11	Second 3 Online courses delivered (MCs and RDMs)	Task 8.1	3 courses delivered 75 attendees involved	Bimester 15 April 2025
12	Second 2 Learning session/Action Research sessions delivered	Task 8.2	2 Learning session/ Action Research Sessions delivered; 40 participants involved	Bimester 15 April 2025

7.1 List of WP8 deliverables

Below is the list of WP8 deliverables as reported in the Project DoW:

- **D8.1** Planning document for the activities related to the capacity building and training.
 - Due to M3 (January 2023)
- **D8.2** Report on software specifications about the online platform for training.

- Due to M12 (October 2023)
- **D8.3** First Report on initiatives related to capacity building and training (online courses, learning session and action research session, higher education courses).
- Due to M18 (April 2024)
- **D8.4** Technical report on the online data analysis software for training.
- Due to M18 (April 2024)
- **D8.5** Second Report on initiatives related to capacity building and training (online courses, learning session and action research session, higher education courses).
- Due to M30 (April 2025)

8. CONCLUSIONS

The present deliverable introduced the framework of the training activities envisioned in the context of the WP8 of the FOSSR project, titled “Capacity building and training”, and demonstrated the achievement of the 1-2-3 milestones associated with the WP.

The Work Package, coordinated by CNR-IRCrES, will offer a variety of training opportunities throughout the project's duration, including (i) online training courses (Methodological Courses and Research Data Management Courses); (ii) participatory sessions (Learning Sessions and Action Research Sessions); (iii) Course at Master level and positions at PhD level (a “Master di Secondo Livello in Social Data Science” and the opening of PhD positions at various Italian universities). The formats and characteristics of training initiatives presented in this document can be subject to adjustments over the project's duration, due to potential improving opportunities or unpredictable constraints.

One of the main commitments of the FOSSR project is to support the education of the next generation of data scientists by improving scholars' and stakeholders' skills in accessing, analyzing, managing, querying, and interpreting data related to the research infrastructures involved in the project, as well as fostering reflective learning and interactions between researchers and societal actors.

9. LIST OF ACRONYMS

Table 2 – List of acronyms and meaning

ACRONYM	Description
ARS	Action Research Session
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CFU	Credito Formativo Universitario (University Educational Credit)
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-IRCrES	Istituto di Ricerca sulla Crescita Economica Sostenibile del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Research Institute on Sustainable Economic Growth of the National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-IRPPS	Istituto delle Ricerche sulla Popolazione e le Politiche Sociali del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies of the National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-ISMED	Istituto di Studi sul Mediterraneo del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Institute for Studies on the Mediterranean of the National Research Council of Italy)
CNR-ISTC	Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie della Cognizione del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Institute for Cognitive Sciences and Technologies of the National Research Council of Italy)
DoW	Description of Work
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FOSSR	Fostering Open science in Social Science Research
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IT	Information and Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LS	Learning Session
M(X)	Month (number)
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (Italian Minister of University and Research)
MC	Methodological Course
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NRRP	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
OTC	Online Training Course
PhD	Philosophiae Doctor
PS	Participatory Session
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RDMC	Research Data Management Course

RI	Research Infrastructure
RISIS	Research Infrastructure for Science, technology and Innovation policy Studies
SDS	Social Data Science
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
UO	Unità Operativa (Operating Unit)
WP	Work Package